

Supplementary Figures S6-S8

Figure S6 Relationships between mean SPAD values and the genotypes of the three major

quantitative trait loci (QTLs). Boxplots showing the phenotypic values of recombinant inbred lines (RILs) (y-axis) in relation to their genotypes at the three major QTLs (x-axis). The horizontal line inside each box represents median value. Box range is the first and third quantile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quantile + 1.5*interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quantile – 1.5*IQR. (a) The phenotypic values of RILs separately shown for Hitomebore or Kaluheenati genotypes at the single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) on chr01:5692791. (b) The phenotypic values of RILs separately shown for Hitomebore or Kaluheenati genotypes at the SNP on chr03:1376034. (c) The phenotypic values of RILs separately shown for Hitomebore or Kaluheenati genotypes at the SNP on chr07:25128206.

A) Combination 1

Figure S7A Relationships between phenotypic values of chlorophyll content and genotypes of the two epistatic single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in Combination 1 and quantitative trait loci (QTLs) as identified by genome-wide association study. Boxplots showing the phenotypic values of recombinant inbred lines with different combinations of

genotypes at SNPs on chr06:24463185, chr09:18306488, and QTLs (chr01:5692791, chr03:1376034, and chr07:25128206). The horizontal line inside each box represents median value. Box range is the first and third quartile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quartile + 1.5*interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quartile – 1.5*IQR. The x-axis shows the combinations of genotypes. The y-axis shows phenotypic values.

B) Combination 2

Figure S7B Relationships between phenotypic values of chlorophyll content and genotypes of the two epistatic single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in Combination 2 and quantitative trait loci (QTLs) as identified by genome-wide association study. Boxplots showing the phenotypic values of recombinant inbred lines with different combinations of

genotypes at SNPs on chr03:9948500, chr06:2900658, and QTLs (chr01:5692791, chr03:1376034, and chr07:25128206). The horizontal line inside each box represents median value. Box range is the first and third quantile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quantile + 1.5*interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quantile – 1.5*IQR. The x-axis shows the combinations of genotypes. The y-axis shows phenotypic values.

C) Combination 3

Figure S7C Relationships between phenotypic values of chlorophyll content and genotypes of the two epistatic single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in Combination 3 and quantitative trait loci (QTLs) as identified by genome-wide association study. Boxplots showing the phenotypic values of recombinant inbred lines with different combinations of genotypes at SNPs on chr09:12263185, chr10:8212236, and QTLs (chr01:5692791,

chr03:1376034, and chr07:25128206). The horizontal line inside each box represents median value. Box range is the first and third quartile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quartile + 1.5*interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quartile – 1.5*IQR. The x-axis shows the combinations of genotypes. The y-axis shows phenotypic values.

D) Combination 4

Genotype
 chr01: 5692791 (QTL) ...
 chr06: 490627 ...
 x
 chr11: 17282493 ...

Hitomebore				Kaluheenati			
Hito	Hito	Kalu	Kalu	Hito	Hito	Kalu	Kalu
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu

Genotype
 chr03: 1376034 (QTL) ...
 chr06: 490627 ...
 x
 chr11: 17282493 ...

Hitomebore				Kaluheenati			
Hito	Hito	Kalu	Kalu	Hito	Hito	Kalu	Kalu
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu

Genotype
 chr07: 25128206 (QTL) ...
 chr06: 490627 ...
 x
 chr11: 17282493 ...

Hitomebore				Kaluheenati			
Hito	Hito	Kalu	Kalu	Hito	Hito	Kalu	Kalu
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu	Hito	Kalu

Figure S7D Relationships between phenotypic values of chlorophyll content and genotypes of the two epistatic single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in Combination 4 and quantitative trait loci (QTLs) as identified by genome-wide association study. Boxplots showing the phenotypic values of recombinant inbred lines with different combinations of genotypes at SNPs on chr06:490627, chr11:17282493, and QTLs (chr01:5692791, chr03:1376034, and chr07:25128206). The horizontal line inside each box represents median value. Box range is the first and third quartile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quartile + 1.5*interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quartile – 1.5*IQR. The x-axis shows the combinations of genotypes. The y-axis shows phenotypic values.

E) Combination 5

Figure S7E Relationships between phenotypic values of chlorophyll content and genotypes of the two epistatic single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in Combination 5 and quantitative trait loci (QTLs) as identified by genome-wide association study. Boxplots showing the phenotypic values of recombinant inbred lines with different combinations of

genotypes at SNPs on chr01:5223450, chr03:3960659, and QTLs (chr01:5692791, chr03:1376034, and chr07:25128206). The horizontal line inside each box represents median value. Box range is the first and third quartile. The whisker extends to last datum less than the third quartile + 1.5*interquartile range (IQR) and the first datum greater than the first quartile – 1.5*IQR. The x-axis shows the combinations of genotypes. The y-axis shows phenotypic values.

Figure S8A DNA sequence alignment of the variant part in the *OsAld-Y* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *OsAld-Y* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding regions are indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of the *OsAld-Y* gene for Hitomebore, Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Nipponbare and Hitomebore had two deletions in the 5' untranslated region of *OsAld-Y*. All alignment results are in Zenodo

([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://zenodo.org/record/3688821)).

Figure S8B DNA sequence alignment of the variant part in the *CYO1* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *OsCYO1* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding regions are indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of the *OsCYO1* gene for Hitomebore, Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Nipponbare and Hitomebore had 38 deletions in the 3' untranslated region of *OsCYO1*. All alignment results are in Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://zenodo.org/record/3688821)).

Figure S8C DNA sequence alignment of the variant part in the *OsCAB1* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *OsCAB1* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding regions is indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of the *OsCAB1* gene for Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Hitomebore did not have *OsCAB1*. Kaluheenati had a substitution in the coding region. All alignment results are in Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://zenodo.org/record/3688821)).

<i>OscpSRP43</i> Hitomebore	1	AGGT TAAAGTTCTGCTCAACTCAAAAATTATCAAAGCGCT	40
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Kaluheenati	1	AGG C TAAAGTTCTGCTCAACTCAAAAATTATCAAAGCGCT	40
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Nipponbare	1	AGGT TAAAGTTCTGCTCAACTCAAAAATTATCAAAGCGCT	40
AGGT TAAAGTTCTGCTCAACTCAAAAATTATCAAAGCGCT			
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Hitomebore	41	AATGATACATTTTGCAGCAGCACAAACATTTTATCCCGTT	80
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Kaluheenati	41	AATGATACATTTTGCAGCAGCACAAACATTTTATCCCGTT	80
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Nipponbare	41	AATGATACATTTTGCAGCAGCACAAACATTTTATCCCGTT	80
AATGATACATTTTGCAGCAGCACAAACATTTTATCCCGTT			
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Hitomebore	81	CTGT TAAACACAGCAAAACCAGGAAGAATCGAACACCCTC	120
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Kaluheenati	81	CTGT T A TACACAGCAAAACCAGGAAGAATCGAACACCCTC	120
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Nipponbare	81	CTGT TAAACACAGCAAAACCAGGAAGAATCGAACACCCTC	120
CTGT TAAACACAGCAAAACCAGGAAGAATCGAACACCCTC			
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Hitomebore	321	TTGTTGACGACGGCCTCCGCGACGGCGTACTCCAGCCCGG	360
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Kaluheenati	321	TTGTT C GACGACGGCCTCCGCGACGGCGTACTCCAGCCCGG	360
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Nipponbare	321	TTGTTGACGACGGCCTCCGCGACGGCGTACTCCAGCCCGG	360
TTGTTGACGACGGCCTCCGCGACGGCGTACTCCAGCCCGG			
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Hitomebore	641	CTCCGGCTCGGGCGCCAGCTCCAGCAGCGCGCGCACGGCC	680
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Kaluheenati	641	CTCCGGCTCGGGCGCCAGCTCCAGCAG C AGCGCGCACGGCC	680
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Nipponbare	641	CTCCGGCTCGGGCGCCAGCTCCAGCAGCGCGCGCACGGCC	680
CTCCGGCTCGGGCGCCAGCTCCAGCAGCGCGCGCACGGCC			
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Hitomebore	841	CCGCGTCCGGGGTACGCCGACGCGTCTCGTCCGCGAGTAG	880
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Kaluheenati	841	CCGCGTCCGGGGTACGCCGACGCGTCTCGTCCGCGAG C AGTAG	880
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Nipponbare	841	CCGCGTCCGGGGTACGCCGACGCGTCTCGTCCGCGAGTAG	880
CCGCGTCCGGGGTACGCCGACGCGTCTCGTCCGCGAGTAG			
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Hitomebore	1201	GACGAAGCCGGAAAGGGACGGTGATGGAGAGGGCTGGAGT	1240
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Kaluheenati	1201	GACGAAGCC G TAAAGGGACGGTGATGG A AGGGCTGGAGT	1240
<i>OscpSRP43</i> Nipponbare	1201	GACGAAGCCGGAAAGGGACGGTGATGGAGAGGGCTGGAGT	1240
GACGAAGCCGGAAAGGGACGGTGATGGAGAGGGCTGGAGT			

Figure S8D DNA sequence alignment of the variant part in the *OscpSRP43* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *OscpSRP43* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding region is indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of the *OscpSRP43* gene for Hitomebore, Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Kaluheenati had six substitutions in the coding region and one substitution in the 5' untranslated region in *OscpSRP43*. All alignment results are in Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3688821)).

Figure S8E DNA sequence alignment of the variant part in the *OsLFNR2* gene. Top: a simplified scheme of *OsLFNR2* gene structure and the region shown in the alignment. Coding regions are indicated by orange color. Bottom: aligned genome sequences of the *OsLFNR2* gene for Hitomebore, Kaluheenati, and Nipponbare (reference genome). Kaluheenati had a 10-bp deletion in the coding region of *OsLFNR2*. All alignment results are in Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.3688821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3688821)).